

The [International Committee for Future Accelerators](#) (ICFA) was created in 1976 by the Particle and Fields Division of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics (IUPAP) to promote international collaboration towards construction and use of accelerators for high energy physics.

The [Beam Dynamics Panel of ICFA](#) encourages and promotes collaboration on beam dynamics studies for present and future accelerators via workshops and regularly appearing newsletters dedicated to selected themes –coordinated by an issue editor. The spectrum of beam dynamics themes includes medium energy and high energy / high luminosity electron facilities / colliders as well as medium energy and high energy / high intensity hadron facilities. The series of such newsletters started in 1987. Newsletter #1 to #78 are available from the [CERN publishing platform](#).

Publication of the Beam Dynamics Newsletter as [Special Issue of the Journal of Instrumentation](#) started in 2020 with Newsletter #79. It includes a general report with forewords/news from the panel chair (editor in chief) and the issue editor as well as reports from past workshops/conferences, PhD thesis abstracts and other reports; followed by papers submitted from individual authors on the special theme of the issue.